

Efficient Asymmetric Synthesis of Carbohydrates by Aldolase Nano-Confined in Lipidic Cubic Mesophases

Tao Zhou,[†] Jijo J. Vallooran,^{†,‡} Salvatore Assenza,[†] Anna Szekrenyi,[¶] Pere
Clapés,[¶] and Raffaele Mezzenga^{*,†}

[†]*Department of Health Science and Technology, ETH Zurich, Schmelzbergstrasse 9, 8092
Zürich, Switzerland*

[‡]*Department of Chemistry, University of Zurich, Winterthurerstrasse 190, 8057 Zurich,
Switzerland*

[¶]*Biotransformation and Bioactive Molecules Group, Instituto de Química Avanzada de
Cataluña, IQAC-CSIC Jordi Girona 18-26, 08034 Barcelona, Spain*

E-mail: raffaele.mezzenga@hest.ethz.ch

Abstract

Class-I aldolases are known for efficiently catalyzing stereoselective aldol-addition reactions in bulk aqueous media, and considerable efforts are currently being devoted to engineer the enzyme in order to optimize its activity and stability, primarily by modulating the hydrophobicity of the catalytic active site. Here, we opt for a different strategy based on choosing a nanoconfined environment favorable to the enzyme. We report the observation of enhanced activity and stability of a class-I aldolase, D-fructose-6-phosphate aldolase from *E. coli* (FSA), when incorporated into lipidic cubic mesophases (LCMs), a class of biomimetic amphiphilic complex fluids employed in several nanotechnology applications. We infer that this improved in-meso performance is

achieved by optimal location of the FSA in the LCMs, as a result of the known interaction between the residues of FSA and the glycerol moieties, which serve as the lipid head groups and thus locate along the amphiphilic interface encompassing the whole LCM. This continuous interface ensures increased accessibility of the catalytic reaction center to substrates and high activity in LCM.

Asymmetric aldol addition, one of the most exploited carbon-carbon bond-forming reactions, has witnessed significant progress during past decades.¹⁻³ The ability to generate two chiral centers has allowed the synthesis of a wide range of naturally occurring as well as synthetic polyhydroxylated products, enabling the exploration of their biological roles and the assessment of their therapeutic potential.⁴⁻⁷ In order to fully exploit these products, specific catalytic asymmetric methods need to be developed which can provide the desired products with high yield. The traditional approaches for synthesizing enantiomerically pure compounds often require multistep preparative routes with low yields, which reduce sustainability of the overall process.^{8,9} Therefore, biocatalysis by enzymes belonging to the aldolase family has received considerable attention in recent years.¹⁰⁻¹⁴ These enzymes convert their substrates into aldol products with high specificity under mild conditions, but also with great control over the relative and absolute configurations of the created stereogenic centers.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Many efforts have been directed to increasing the stability and activity of aldolases using methods such as directed evolution, reaction engineering, and de novo enzyme design.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ Recently, Clapés et al. developed a simple procedure for the preparation of aldose carbohydrates and their derivatives by employing engineered D-fructose-6-phosphate aldolase (FSA), which belongs to the class-I aldolase family.²⁰

Aldol reactions of naturally occurring class-I aldolases play crucial roles in the central sugar metabolic pathways of all organisms including animals, plants, protozoa, and algae where these reactions are occurring in a confined, crowded amphipathic environment rather than in bulk aqueous media.²¹ The active site of class-I aldolase enzymes consists of a conserved lysine residue which activates the nucleophile via Schiff base with subsequent forma-

tion of a transient enamine intermediate and an acid–base residue which can be the hydroxyl group of a tyrosine or the carboxylate group of an aspartate or glutamate residues.^{22–24} These amino acids form a hydrophobic “reaction pocket” at their active site that diminishes contacts between bulk water and the reaction transition states.^{25,26} Recently, an elegant work from Obexer et al. showed that artificial aldolase enzymes with a computationally designed hydrophobic pocket near the active site enables to reach catalytic activities similar to the wild-type class-I aldolase.²⁷

Enzyme immobilization has been widely used to improve the performances of enzymes.^{28–32} Therefore, although aldolase biocatalysis can efficiently be performed in water, an amphiphilic reaction medium may also be beneficial because of the presence of the conserved amphipathic reaction center. In this regard, a promising host for aldol reactions is provided by lipidic cubic mesophases (LCMs). Within these systems, a single, continuous lipid bilayer defines two sets of interpenetrating yet noncommunicating water channels characterized by a triply periodic structure.³³ Because of their biomimetic structural characteristics and thermodynamic stability in excess water, LCMs are excellent host matrices for membrane protein crystallization and enzymatic reactions.^{34–38} The nanosized water channels present therein provide a unique environment, where enzymatic reactions follow different kinetics as compared with solution.³⁸ Here, we show that D-fructose-6-phosphate aldolase (FSA) can be successfully confined in LCMs, where it outperforms the results obtained in bulk solution not only in terms of stability but also for reactivity (Scheme 1).

The nanostructure of the LCMs used for this study was readily identified by small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). The positions of the Bragg peaks according to the sequence $\sqrt{6} : \sqrt{8} : \sqrt{14} : \sqrt{16} : \sqrt{20} : \sqrt{22}$ (Figure 1) are the fingerprint of a LCM with double-gyroid symmetry (*Ia3d* group). The corresponding lattice parameter was equal to 12.10 nm (neat cubic phase), and the diameter of the water channel calculated to be 2.82 nm (section 1.3 in the Supporting Information). In the presence of FSA, the slight increase of the lattice parameter (12.44 nm) and the size of water channels (2.91 nm) indicated the incorporation of

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Scheme 1: Schematic Representation of FSA^{A129T/S166G} Catalyzing the Formation of Carbohydrates in the LCMs and in Bulk Solution

the enzyme in the cubic lattice. Moreover, the symmetry of the LCM was preserved during the entire course of biocatalysis.

The enzyme FSA^{A129T/S166G} can catalyze the stereoselective formation of d-idose (3a) via a one-pot reaction.²¹ In this synthesis, at first, glycolaldehyde (1a) is dimerized into d-threose (2a) (Table 1). Then, a second addition of 1a to the acyclic form of 2a produces 3a. The trimerization of 1a is slow in solution, with a yield of only 30% of 3a (Figure 2a, 2b). In contrast, when the enzyme was incorporated in the LCM, the trimerization rate of 1a was accelerated dramatically. Indeed, after 5 h, the product D-idose already dominated the mixture, while in solution even after 24 h byproduct (2a) was still dominating (Figure 2a,b). Both the reaction rate and the yield were much larger for the enzyme incorporated in LCMs than in bulk solution (Figure 2c). The kinetics data were fitted according to the following formula³⁹

$$[P] = \frac{\nu_0}{\eta} (1 - e^{-\eta t}) \quad (1)$$

where $[P]$ is the yield, while ν_0 and η are the initial slope and the saturation time scale, respectively. The obtained values show that reactions in the mesophase outperform the ones in solution both in initial speed (by a factor of 4) and final yield (by a factor of 2.5), as we report in Table S1.

Apart from efficiently catalyzing the formation of D-idose, LCM-embedded FSA^{A129T/S166G}

Figure 1: SAXS profile of lipidic cubic mesophases (LCMs). Black: pure LCM prepared by mixing 75% monolinolein and 25% buffer solution; green: 3 mg/mL enzyme FSA^{A129T/S166G} loaded in the LCM; purple: 0.05 mmol/mL reactant glycolaldehyde loaded in the LCM; pink: both enzyme and reactant loaded in the LCM and SAXS measurement performed immediately after preparing the sample; orange: same as pink, but SAXS was measured after completion of the enzymatic reaction.

Table 1. One-Pot Synthesis of Carbohydrates Catalyzed by FSA^{A129T/S166G}

reactant	product	yield	
		in LCM	in solution
a	3a	>80%	30%
b	3b	>95%	33%
c	3c	74%	35%

Figure 2: HPLC profile of the formation of D-idose in the LCM (a) and in bulk solution (b) after different reaction times. (c) Time progression curves for the enzymatic synthesis of D-idose. (d) CD spectrum of enzyme FSA^{A129T/S166G} in the LCM and in bulk solution. Data are only shown from 200 nm due to strong absorbance at shorter wavelengths in LCMs.

shows a better performance also in synthesizing other functional carbohydrates. As shown in Figure S10, after 7 h the yield of L-xylose in the LCM had already reached around 90%, and the final yield was more than 95% with full stereoselectivity. In solution, even after 24 h the yield was below 50%. The excellent catalyzing property of incorporated enzymes is also preserved in the synthesis of 6-deoxy-D-idose (3c). In solution, enzyme FSA^{A129T/S166G} demonstrated low activity for the synthesis of 6-deoxy-D-idose (3c), with a final yield of only 35%. Conversely, the relative yield was increased to 70% if the enzyme was incorporated into the LCM (Figure S11, S12).

The highly efficient conversion in LCMs is not merely due to the accumulation of reactant in the aqueous channels. Compartmentalization can enhance the yield, but only a little (i.e., a maximum of 25% as shown on the recent publication of Landau et al).⁴⁰ In stark contrast, in our work we see an enhancement up to 3-fold. In addition, we performed aldolase reactions with different water content but same reactant concentration as well as by varying the cubic phase symmetry. Aldolase activity was not influenced by water content or topology (Figure

S6). Indeed, the catalytic activity was preserved even if the symmetry was changed from $Ia\bar{3}d$ to $Pn\bar{3}m$ by increasing the aqueous content to over 30% (Figure S6 and Table S1). However, as soon as bulk excess water coexisted with the LCM, as in the case of 40% aqueous medium, the activity decreased, with both initial speed and final yield reduced by more than 20% (Figure S6 and Table S1). The high activity can be preserved when the lipid is changed to phytantriol, which is a monoglyceride with a slightly different structure compared with dimodan (Figure S7). These data confirm the key role of incorporation of aldolases in the LCM in improving the enzyme activity, which proceeds differently compared with other enzymes, where topology and water content affect the kinetics.^{41–43}

Interestingly, the intensity of CD signal (Figure 2d) in the LCM increased dramatically compared with bulk solution. Also the stability of FSA was greatly enhanced in the mesophase. Even after 4 days, FSA embedded in LCMs remained stable, whereas in solution disappearance of its α helical contents denoted partial or complete denaturation (Figure 2d).⁴⁴

Further insights are provided by a closer inspection of the structural features of FSA^{A129T/S166G}. As only two mutations differentiate it from the wild-type form of the enzyme, it is reasonable to assume a similar structure. FSA is a protein complex composed of 10 identical units (PDB code: 1L6W²⁶). Each monomer consists of an amphipathic α -helix and an α/β barrel (Figure 3a).²⁶ The catalytic lysine residue, Lys85, together with the two other residues Ala165, Asp6 are known to form effective ligand interaction with the glycerol moiety, which connect to a fatty acid via a transesterification reaction to form the lipid (Figure 3a).^{26,45,46} Thus, when the lipid forms cubic phases with water, the catalytic reaction center of FSA is expected to be found in close proximity of glycerol (i.e., at the interface between the hydrophobic alkyl chain and water). The amphipathic α helix of a subunit runs across the C-terminal side of the α/β barrel of a neighboring monomer, which is predominantly hydrophobic, where it shields the catalytic active site (Figure 3b). In aqueous solutions, the substrate needs to access this conserved amphipathic region to form products. It is well-known that amphipathic α helices

are usually partitioned in the lipidic bilayers,^{47–49} which may be the reason behind the high stability of the enzyme. The overall shape of the decamer is a hollow disk with a diameter equal to approximately 10.5 nm and a height of 6.5 nm, with an inner channel diameter of 3.0 nm passing through the molecule (Figure 3c). As mentioned before, the LCM consists of two sets of water channels surrounded by a lipid bilayer. For the *Ia3d* employed in the present study, the lipid bilayer has an average thickness of 3.2 nm, while the water channels have a diameter of around 2.8 nm. These numbers suggest an intriguing geometrical arrangement for the enzyme. We conjecture that FSA orients its axis along one channel and is centered in the middle of it. In this way, the enzyme can accommodate most parts of each monomer in the lipid bilayer (which defines an annulus of total diameter equal to $3.2 + 3.2 + 2.8$ nm = 9.2 nm), while the inner space defined by its hollow cylindrical structure is located in the water channels. We stress that the thickness of the lipid bilayer varies locally; thus, the values computed from the SAXS measurements are only averages. The membrane can adapt its local shape in order to efficiently accommodate foreign materials.^{34–38} Compared with a neat cubic phase, we have indeed observed a slight increase in the lattice parameter for FSA-loaded cubic phases, which can be attributed to the incorporation of FSA, mostly partitioned within the hydrophobic domains. Conversely, incorporation of macromolecules, ions, and charged nanoparticles in LCM water nanochannels is well-known to reduce the lattice parameter rather than increasing it.⁵⁰ Because there is only one FSA decamer per 75 cubic lattices (section 1.3 in the Supporting Information), only a minor swelling was observed (Figure 1). The proposed geometrical arrangement within the *Ia3d* cubic mesophase is shown in Figure 3d,e, (see Figure 3f,g for the *Pn3m* case). Remarkably, after fitting the FSA inside the LCM, the α helix and the active site are located exactly at the interface between lipid bilayer and water channels. Therefore, the hydrophilic reactant can get access to the active site more easily than in bulk solution, as shown by Figure 3d,f (arrows).

In order to verify the generality of this medium engineering, we have further performed cross-aldol additions of glycolaldehyde using wild-type FSA and another FSA variant (FSA^{A129S}).

Figure 3: (a) Monomer structure of wild-type FSA; the red ball-and-stick model represent the lysine residue at the active site (Lys85); the orange is the alanine residue (Ala165); the magenta is the aspartate residue (Asp6); the yellow is the ligand glycerol. (b) Dimer structure of wild-type FSA where the amphipathic α helix of a subunit runs across the C-terminal side of the α/β barrel of a neighboring subunit and shields the active site. (c) Decameric structure of wild-type FSA, where red arrows indicate the active sites. (d,e) enzyme entrapped in a LCM with $Ia3d$ symmetry: the lipid bilayer is depicted in yellow; the water channels are in light blue; the light green, between blue and yellow regions, corresponds to the interface. (f,g) enzyme entrapped in a LCM with $Pn3m$ symmetry.

As shown in Table 2, better performances of both enzymes in LCM are obtained, compared with in solution. The yield of 1-deoxy-D-xylulose catalyzed via wild-type FSA in LCM can be enhanced to more than 80%, from 57% in solution. For FSA^{A129S}, the enhancement in LCM is more than 2-fold. All these data show that the medium engineering reported here can efficiently enhance the performances of enzymes via locating the active site at the amphiphilic interface, facilitating reactants access to the active site. In addition, previous works in our group have shown that incorporating enzymes into LCMs can improve their reusability in excess water,⁴³ and the product can be simply extracted out via column chromatography (section 2 in the Supporting Information).

In conclusion, we have shown that the activity and stability of aldolase can be significantly enhanced by incorporating the enzyme in lipidic cubic mesophases. These results are rationalized in light of the expected facilitated access to the catalytic reaction center, located at the lipid–water interface due to nanoconfinement. We expect that this improved

Table 2. Asymmetric Cross-Aldol Additions of Glycolaldehyde

		yield		
reactant	product	enzyme	in LCM	in solution
4d	6d	wild-type FSA	82%	57%
4d	6d	FSA ^{A129S}	83%	40%
4e	6e	FSA ^{A129S}	86%	39%

activity and stability in amphipathic mediums would also be observed for other members of the transaldolases family as they have similar structures.^{51,52} Extensive knowledge arising from these biochemical studies will pave the way to design tailored biocatalysts for future sustainable production of an expanded molecular range of complex polyfunctional targets.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Dr. Antoni Sánchez-Ferrer for useful discussion about HPLC separation. T.Z. acknowledges the China Scholarship Council and ETH Zurich for financial support of this work. Salvatore Assenza acknowledges support from the Swiss National Science Foundation under grant no. 200021_162355. A.S. and P.C. acknowledge the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (MINECO), and the Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER) (grant no. CTQ2015-63563-R).

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